

EARTH SCIENCES

ECOLOGICAL - GEOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF OBJECTS OF NATURAL HERITAGE OF THE ABSHERON REGION OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

Absheron - considerable peninsula in Azerbaijan, region of crucial development, emphasized an exceptionally important area of Country in economic and ecological position.

Being dominant economic region, Absheron is the area of conflict of multisided businesses and balanced natural ecosystems. Absheron - is economic district of prompt growing financial state and unique natural treasures.

Absheron region, where capital city Baku is situated and one of initial national parks of the Country launched at the tip of Peninsula by the Cape Shah-Dili.

Considering geomorphological, climatic, hydrological and hydrogeological features of Absheron region we've highlighted exclusive phenomenon - famous mud volcanoes of Absheron - Gobustan, area for the first Geopark of Azerbaijan in nearest future.

Natural treasures of Absheron make this Peninsula a fascinating area for singular introduction of reciprocal attitude of Nature and Society (in ambiguous meaning) : confrontation of high-powered links of economic profits and conservation challenges.

Keywords: Absheron Peninsula, economic development, nature protection, natural phenomena, climate, rivers, lakes, groundwaters, landscape, mud volcanoes, soil resources, territory modeling.

Purpose of research

Scrutinizing of modern landscape dynamics of Absheron peninsula, researching on endemic biodiversity, identifying rare and endangered species of plants and animals, preserving flora and fauna in study area based on background of anthropogenic impact and analyzing most efficient use of natural components, as well as comprehensive environmental survey of subject field.

Physical-geographical state of morphological structures of coastal lines of Caspian Sea and ridges of the Greater Caucasus covering Absheron peninsula and these natural components have decisive influence to major climatic factors, contributed by changes and diversity of atmospheric processes - air fronts, solar radiation, impacts of global and local circulations and surface temperature.

Features of *climatic resources* of the Absheron peninsula

Largely weather conditions of Absheron peninsula characterized as the climate of semi-deserts and dry steppes with mild winters and arid hot summers, described in academic assignments as the dry subtropical zone. Chosen research region is one of the least rainy and most windy areas of Republic of Azerbaijan. Despite of limited area of Absheron peninsula, certain changes of temperature over the year are predominant - main reasons for amplitude of temperature are being formed by multiplicity of relief and distance to the Caspian Sea [7].

There are several meteorological stations at the territory of Absheron peninsula. Average of annual winter temperature varies between 13.5°C and 14.4°C. During four summer months average of thermal conditions present over 20°C. None-freezing period lasts about 268 - 293 days; annual precipitation approximates 160 - 250 mm, with differentiation between northern (rainier) and southern parts of the Absheron peninsula.

Table 1.

Seasonal climatic indicators of the Absheron peninsula*

Meteorological stations	Years	Seasons												Average annual
		Spring			Summer			Autumn			Winter			
		III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	I	II	
Baku	2021	8,8	12	17	25	26	28	21	17	10	5	3	4,2	15,1
	2022	6,2	10	19	23	25	27	22	17	10	7	6	4,3	15
	2023	10,5	12	18	22	25	27	21	16	12	5	1	3,4	14,7
Sumgayit	2021	9,1	12	17	24	25	28	22	18	11	6	2	4,2	15,2
	2022	6,4	11	18	23	25	27	23	18	10	7	6	4,8	15,6
	2023	10,4	12	17	22	25	27	22	16	12	5	1	3,5	14,9

*Data of records of the Department of Meteorology of the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of Azerbaijan - Department of Hydrometeorology - based on annual data (2021-2023)

According to perennial database of observations of Meteorological Bureau of Baku, average of annual temperature - 14.2°C, while absolute records - max (+42°C Jule'2000) and min (January'2000 -15°C) [8].

Northern directed winds - khazri - cooling air in summer and extremely cold in winter. Southern winds - gilavar - bring hot in summer, while during winter cool slightly. Average of wind speed is 4-6 m/s for entire territory of Absheron peninsula. Considering to the days of strong winds, the Absheron peninsula has the highest wind speeds up to 21m/sec for 95 days in Sumgayit, 40 days in settlement Mashtagha, 37 days in the Island Pir Allahy and 35 days in capital Baku.

During 2022, mainly northern winds are captured and account for 1/3 of the total winds. Average of annual velocity of wind reaches 6.7 m/s, sometimes 15 - 20 m/s and even 30 - 40 m/s. The average annual speed of south and south-west winds is 7 m/s. Quantity of sunny days with active temperatures varies between 255 - 293.

Annual precipitation amount ~ 240-260 mm and annual evaporation has very high index variation between 1150 and 1250 mm (recorded by Meteorological Department of the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources (MENR) in May - September). Average of annual relative humidity is 68 - 71%, in winter (December-February) 79 - 84% and in summer 52 - 58% [11].

Hydrological assets and groundwater resources of Absheron peninsula. Natural hydrographic network of Absheron peninsula has been shaped under dominance of various indicators and refers to surface water sources (rivers, lakes) and groundwaters as well as thermal water wellsprings [3].

Rivers: Pirsaaatchay, Jeyrankechmez, Sumgayitchay along with other small rivers flowing from Gobustan area and starting from the mid-mountainous zones are often dried up in summer because of lack of rains.

River Sumgayitchay flows from NW to SE and floods occur in spring (average from 100 - 150 to 250 - 300 days a year). Increase of water consumption of river observed mainly during spring & autumn rains, and least during summer months.

Longest waterway of the region - River Pirsaaatchay - length - 119 km and basin - 2280 km²; the source of the River Pirsaaatchay originates from the southern slopes of the Major Caucasus (2400 m), most of flows come by rainfalls (80%), partly snowwaters (14%) and groundwaters (16%). Average of annual water consumption of river - 1.55 m³/sec, 60-70% of the annual flow being observed through spring and summer seasons [3].

Lakes: more than 200 small-scale lakes in Absheron, covering about 2.5% of area, subdivided by origin to endogenous (tectonic), exogenous and anthropogenic groups. Most of lakes are getting dry during the hottest months of year and only 10 lakes have aquatic areas larger than 1 km², relatively size-able lakes are located at the central parts of the Peninsula. To category of lakes of tectonic origin include Lake Boyukshor, Lake Masazyr and others.

Lakes of erosion - abrasive origin have been shaped alongside separation of seawater by sedimentary deposits.

Lake Duzlu - by the S of settlement Zyk and Lake Gyrmzy by the SW of Baku are examples of increased anthropogenic impacts on lake basins over last decades. Outcomes of these effects - both morphological and hydro-physical properties of lakes have been changed thoroughly. Lakes of Peninsula are largely saturated with shallow and salt-soluble salts, most of which have dry characters during summer periods. Sediments, collected at the bottom of the lakes of the Absheron Peninsula have medical significance and these sediments or mud are widely used for treatment of several diseases.

Lake Boyukshor - located at the core of Peninsula ~12 m above ISL, only SW coast of lake is relatively higher; some settlements (Balakhany, Sabunchu, Boyukshor, Binagady and others) since centuries located by the lake edges.

Lake Binagadi - consists 3 wetlands and has unique landscape type in terms of biodiversity and systematics of natural monuments; by the W part of lake there are two famous geological monuments - mud volcanoes of Keykari and Abikh. Mud volcano Keykari - very fascinating natural monument, in terms of scale

and erosion activity, therefore included to the List of State Nature Monuments of Azerbaijan.

Lake Gyrgyzy - located by the SW of Baku, during geological collapse time, this lake had been a gulf of the Caspian Sea and was subsequently isolated from the Sea as a result of lowering of level; mirrow surface of the lake is 700 ha, capacity of water is 8.3 mlnm³.

Lake Khojahasan - located at the western extremity of Baku, by the northern part of Yasamal Valley, absolute height 14m, has an elongated shape - 3.3 km through N to S & about 6 km through W to E; surface area ~1.5 km², max depth - 6 to 8 m.

Lake Masazyr - positioned 8m above ISL at the NW of Absheron peninsula; settlement Masazir is situated by the SW of Lake and settlement Novkhany by the NE. Shape of lake Masazyr has roundabout shape, covering is about 10 km², length - 5 km and width - 3 km. Water masses of lake are set up by precipitation and several springs., and according to the climatic peculiarities during summer seasons water level reaches its maximum drying depth, but no more than 0.5 m.

Temperature of water fluctuated around 30°C or up. During summer months lake is highly saturated with salinization level and mineralization degree reaches over 300 g/l.

Lake Mirzealadi - detected on 0.9 km of the NW of Absheron peninsula, 0.9 km E of the Masazyr Range and W of Binagadi - Novkhany highway. The eastern coastal slopes reach 12 - 15 m, coastlines are partially smooth with length of ~12.5 km. Area have developed by karstic relief forms.

Lake Zykh - situated on 26 meters of the S of Absheron peninsula, by the E of Baku Bay and S of settlement Zykh. Connecting waterway of Lake Zykh to the Caspian Sea goes direction of W. Lake is drainless, has elliptical shape and ranges 300 - 350 m in length & 100 - 150 m in width from NW to SE. Deepest central part is no far than 2-3 meters - it's depending of seasonal water level. Temperature of lake's waters achieve ~ 30°C [3, 4].

Table 2.

Main physical and chemical properties of lakes of Absheron [3]

	Lakes	Water surface area of lakes, km	Maximum depth, m	Water transparency, m	The length of the lake, km
1.	Boyukshor	9-15	5-7	0.3	7
2.	Masazyr	6-10	1-2	0.6	4.2
3.	Mirzealadi	2-4	1-4	0.8	3
4.	Gyrgyzy	3-7	1-3	0.5	3.8
5.	Khojahasan	1-2	4-8	0.5	4.1
6.	Zykh	0.1	2-3	0.7	1.7

Groundwaters: there are different spring water sources in Peninsula varying degrees of mineralization, depending of landforms, chemical compositions of soil-forming rocks, climatic conditions and depth of sediments', also stratification of layers; as well as distance from the Caspian Sea [1]. Levels of groundwater by foothills rise 60 cm in spring, autumn & fall and 80-100 cm during summer seasons. Accumulation of toxic salts in soil profiles affect physical and chemical compositions, thus influence to quality of soils. Genesis of water balance of groundwaters of study areas gather by precipitation, rivers, lakes, also Absheron canal as well as leakage from local reservoirs [3].

Groundwaters' table of Peninsula are basically depend on peculiar properties of relief of the and temper of climatic conditions. On-the-spot impact of groundwaters to processes of soil erosion found by the E of Peninsula. At the eastern part of Peninsula, groundwaters' levels sway between 0.5 - 2m and 5 - 7m. Index of mineralization of groundwaters varies ~ 2.5-3g/lit. Orig-

inated from Mt. Garagush and passing toward the Caspian Sea, groundwater levels are increasing noticeably, but chemical compositions presented unchanged.

Despite of considerable depth of groundwaters at the outskirts of city Sumgayit, soil cover at the edge of River Sumgayitchay is saline; reason - majority of saline sediments. Rainwater flows down of the slopes are washing away rocks, due to increased humidity; salts move to bottom of soils. Consequently, highest level of groundwaters occur in February, May and November - December, while lowest marks observed in August - October.

Thermal and mineral waters: Absheron peninsula has sui generic mineral and thermal water deposits. Mineral waters of the Absheron peninsula can be divided to 3 primary groups, according to balneological indicators:

- ❖ Waters without specific components,
- ❖ Sulphide waters,
- ❖ Iodine bromide waters.

Table 3.

Hydro-chemical properties of mineral and thermal water deposits of the Absheron peninsula [3]

Name of the area	Balneology group	Water sources	Minerality, g/l	Temperature, °C	pH	Water debit	Modern use
Surakhani	III	Well	14,3	18	8,6	500000	Balneology
Shikhov	III	Well	16	68	8,2	500000	Resort
Pirallahi	III	Well	8,6	18,5	7,9	400000	Balneology
Mardakan	I	Well	6,8	18	7,2	20000	Sanatorium
Pirshahi	I	Well	7,1	18	7,3	250000	Sanatorium
Sarigaya	I	Spring	7,2	16,8	7	90000	Pansion
Bilgah	I	Spring	7,1	17,4	7,1	45000	Sanatorium
Gala	III	Well	7,3	18.1	7,4	45000	Pansion
Buzovna	I	Well	9.8	17	7,1	200000	Resort

Most of water springs of Peninsula are associated with mud volcanoes (will be described below). Thermal waters also divided to 3 considerable types, depending on temperature of fertile water layers: low temperature (20-50°C), thermal (50-75°C) and high pointed (75-100°C). Rate of mineralization of thermal waters of Absheron peninsula varies among 1 to 10 [3, 4].

Landscape dynamics [9] of the Absheron peninsula - due to the complex natural conditions of the Republic of Azerbaijan, developed landscapes are also characterized by diversity of study territory.

Mud volcanoes are unevenly distributed throughout Azerbaijan, specifically at the region of investigations. There are tiny and massive ones, playing significant role in evolution of modern relief of the Absheron peninsula [2]. Morphologically, mud volcanoes have cone - shaped forms of elevation 5 - 150 m and height up to 400 m. Hills of mud volcanoes correspond to their craters; diameters differ about 400 - 500 m and registered base diameters ~ 6000 - 10000 m.

Dynamic terrain (landscape dynamics) mean of changes on appearance of natural ecosystems, as a precedent of symbiosis of endogenous & exogenous processes [9]. Most of outward forms of endogenous processes of Absheron peninsula found in presence of mud volcanoes. Regardless of wide allocation, phenomenon of mud volcanism studied not circumstantially by geologists and geoscientists. Mud volcanoes mostly developed within western areas of Absheron peninsula, and in southern and south-eastern parts of the costs over lowlands of Caspian seashores. Wide-ranging volcanoes located in western and central parts of region: Hokmali, Binagadi, Saray, Novkhani, Zigilpiri, Keyraki, Abikh, Bokh-Bokha, Boyukdash, Kushhana, Otman-Bozdag, Lokbatan, Shongar and numerous. There are also buried mud volcanoes in Zyxh and Bibiheybat sectors of Peninsula.

Some features of natural phenomena:

- mud volcano Abikh - located 12 km N of Baku, has two craters - one is old (flattened area of 170 cm in diameter), the other one - relatively younger and protected only by the NW locality. Abikh mud volcano has

long period of calm and its eruption activity is much weaker than other similar cinder cones (e.g. Keyraki volcano). The area sheltered by mud cover of the Keyraki and Abikh volcanoes has 700 m with the length of 1100 m,

- mud volcano Bokh-Bokha - tectonically located at the western part of Balakhany - Sabunchu - Ramana block. Trigonometric shape of Bokh-Bokha mud volcano occupies a top of hill, which consists of masses of erupted breccia. Considerable amount of granite also discovered here, as well as heavy oil, flowing from griffons, molds a layer of crust,

- mud volcano Keyraki - located 12 km N of Baku at the W segment of central part of Absheron peninsula; last eruption happened in 2001, column of breccia ejected on 5 - 15m in height, 300m in length and 100m in width, latest eruption covered area larger than 10 ha,

- mud volcano Kushhana - located 2 km S of study area, has elliptical shape; basin is broad and slopes are some inclined, area enveloped by breccia (0.425 km). Geologically structure of this area includes Absheron and Akhjayl sediments. At present the Kushhana mud volcano is in silent mood,

- mud volcano Lokbatan - located 10 - 12 km SW of Baku, near settlement Lokbatan, situated 130m above level of Caspian Sea and 100m above the ground surface. It's one of most active volcanoes of Azerbaijan and particularly eroding every 3 - 10 years volcanic gel. First recorded eruption occurred in 1829. Eruptions occurred also in 1887 and/or 1954 have to be mentioned specially depending on strength of eruption and volume of erosion products. Last activity, lasting twenty-five minutes (2004) and accompanied by a tremor around 10 km; currently undergoing calm period,

- mud volcano Otman Bozdag - occupies crater with diameter of 3,000 m, crater's edges are limited to 6m high dam with steep slopes cut by deep cleats. Pliocene sediments required in geological structure of the mud volcanic region,

- mud volcano Shongar - located 12 km NW of settlement Puta, volcanic area consists hills with low-level slopes. Cracks of 2 - 3 m deep in mud breeding

impede movement on the volcano. Rocks of eruption belong to the Eocene and the Pliocene origin. After last eruption total area of the sack covers about 168 ha,

- mud volcano Zyk - located S of Lake Zyk, by geological structure refers to the Absheron and Akjagyl floors and fertile sediment depositions [2].

Exogenous geological processes - basics of occurrence of features of external geomorphic activities represent terrestrial structure, relief, climate, hydrogeological and engineering-geological conditions as well as tectonic movements. Emphasized on Absheron peninsula - one of the most developed economic regions of the Country, anthropogenic factors have defining influence on important character in genesis and expansion of exogenous geological processes [9].

Recently, impact of anthropogenic factors to geological environment of the Absheron peninsula has intensified [2]. Stronger results of anthropogenic factors are reflected in large-scaled constructions of the Absheron peninsula during the demolition of various water pipes, sewage lines, injection of various volumes of waste into collector layers, disrupting ground flow regime and accumulating groundwater in particular area. Therefore, these erosions are accompanied by increase of sliding, occurrence of surface sedimentation, matter of suffocation processes and intensification of geodynamic processes of Western Absheron landslide areas, including Ahmedly, Masazyr, Zyk, Bayil and Binagady locales:

~ Ahmedly sliding area - slip occurred in SW slopes of General Shykhlin'sky Street in settlement Ahmadly of district Khatai on 26 February, 2012: main reason for these processes - anthropogenic pressure affecting by hydrogeological conditions of area; e.g.: water pipeline accidents, discharge of waste from car garages on the slopes and so on. Following of protection of these areas, walls of garages are being built by iron-concrete constructions at the sliding zone.

~ Masazyr area - main reason of landslides - lack of water management. Thus, have seen records of discharge of wastewater from landslides. The slopes are covered by eluvial - deluvial sediments up to 3m thick, forming massive clay-sand grounds; in order to prevent erosion, water supply of residential dwellings which exist close to the sliding zones were stopped (reference barriers were built) and drainage system highly recommended for the purpose of groundwater management;

~ Zyk area - since construction works have significantly weakened stability of slopes also forced slide and avalanche processes. In several locations along existing ancient sliding area, there are cracks of 30 - 40 m in length, 3 - 10 cm in width and 1.3 m in visible depth. Various cracks and deformations are observed in adjacent private houses; however, construction works are still in progress;

~ Bayil settlement - as a result of construction activities carried out in this location, sliding process have been accelerated, is increases spread of cracks of soil structures, origination of hollows in destroyed area and led to appearance of processes of suffocation;

~ Binagady sliding area - fully composed by stable productive sedimentary deposits. Along the slopes,

these sediments set up masses about 3m thick composed of sands and clay-sand grounds. Leading reason for occurring of process of landslides in settlement Binagady - discharge of sewage into soil layers.

Soils of the Absheron peninsula - gray, alluvial-meadow, saline, sandy, bare rocks and salty clay rocks are representative for the dry subtropical landscapes of study area [5]. Gray and saline soils of Peninsula cover the western and central parts of region and are quintessential by comprehensible distinction of the genetic profile of soils. Also, alluvial-meadow soils have been found line up the valley of River Sumgayitchay. Chloride and sulfate salts prevail in layers of gray soils of Peninsula, granulometric composition of these soils consist of variety of clay (heavy, medium and light clay). However, humus content is low in gray soils, as well as soft soils found in limestones and sands of marine origin. Violation of irrigation norms/regimes in Absheron, inefficient discharge of mining and waste waters, like rising of level of the Caspian Sea cause swamps and salinization of soils. Meliorative measures, such as soil washing and collector-drainage network can be eliminated by salinization. Gray-brown soils are subdivided into typical gray-brown semi-types by genetic spread and exhaustive anthropogenic influences. Gray-brown soils set up in arid subtropical conditions of semi-desert, in-fact, undeveloped gray-brown soils[5].

Saline soils are widely distributed throughout of Absheron peninsula, major reason for salinization is penurious irrigation; bottoms of most of irrigation canals aren't concreted and groundwaters lay close to surface. One of essential causes of soil salinization is evaporation. Saline soils of Absheron peninsula contain chemical composition which is easily soluble from 1 - 3 to 10 - 15%, it's mainly spread in dry steppe and semi-desert landscapes of Absheron. Soil profile of saline areas of Absheron peninsula is scantily stratified and productivity of these lands is poor [6].

Research territory introduced the balanced developed natural landscape system - scenery of Absheron created by peninsula's peculiar physical and geographical conditions, which play essential role in settling up of ecological states, regarding naturally occurring environmental conditions, protection of biodiversity and scales of pollution, mainly anthropogenic power [9].

In process of study Absheron peninsula have been divided (conditionally) to 3 layers:

- first phase review of main scientific and methodological sources concerning of ecological characteristics of Peninsula: geographical location, climatic peculiarities and hydrological properties of region;

- second milestone - general output of field surveys;

- third grade - implementation of modeling methods. External surveys focus on environmental state of natural landscapes, disturbed landscapes of area and modern conditions of surface cover.

Development of natural landscapes of Absheron peninsula besides of peninsula's origination are directly linked to balance of natural factors and various effects

of society [9]. Deterioration of components of ecological state of essential landscapes of Absheron region include naturally devastating events, such as landslides and erosion processes, these events play major role in changing conditions of sustainability of landscapes. Many areas of Absheron peninsula are particularly revealed by wind erosion and water erosion; major factors, affecting development and acceleration of natural erosion - improper use of lands by residents and anthropogenic factors influence increase of eroded areas in region of researches.

Parallel to natural processes, contemporary anthropogenic factors have huge impacts [9] on topography of Absheron peninsula, in many cases - negative influences, therefore some landscapes of the research region has been preserved and typical example - Absheron National Park - specific protected area, encompassed by the narrow SE tip of Peninsula, covering Cape of Shah Dili.

Absheron peninsula as the field of oil and gas extraction and derivative productions, environmental studies on many contaminated terrains are necessary due to studying of eco-geochemical features of landscapes' complexes of polluted areas have scientific and practical value.

During field studies in Absheron peninsula, soil, vegetation and water tests taken from reference points, subsequently, actual data obtained throughout chemical analysis of these samples give some ideas regarding of compound identification of soil resources.

Morphological and genetic features of oil - poisoned soils of Absheron peninsula have been studied over different periods, by result of these researches, fertility model established for oil polluted soils in very high, moderate and poor levels. Light and medium-sized clay-gray oil infected soils are considered as the representative models. Primary properties of these soils are low carbon dioxide difference between the relatively clean areas and gray-brown soils of Peninsula. Indexes of oil pollution are pointed out 26 to 20% in most contaminated areas, 18 to 16% in moderately polluted sectors and 13 to 10% in low poisoned districts.

Absheron peninsula is heavily contaminated by raw oil/oil products and the depth of these polluted segments reach approximately 2.0 - 2.5m. Soil contamination adversely affected morphological and genetic characteristics and physical/chemical functions, as well as alternates of productivity [11].

Absheron peninsula is an efficiently developed industrial and agricultural region. However, due to neglect and poor irrigation, some parts of lands were subjected to salinization and some were contaminated by raw oil, oil products, mineral waters, industrial and domestic wastes and oil well. Depending on categories of repairs carried out in wells, oil and water droplets are transported to specific distance by wind and pollute of those areas. According to the winds speed and micro-elastic conditions, areas of oil distribution reach 30 - 40 m at investigations' territories.

Process of modeling of territory substitutes of object of research process and gives new point of view on terrain [11]. Modeling is a role of human activities in

creating and clarifying resources in assess of impacts in progress of land use.

Territory modeling, as a research method, plays important role in understanding impact of society on nature and exploring ways to positive changes; implementing landscape models to the particular cases to environment in Absheron, as methods of visible features of an area of land pattering are used to investigate new facts and define sustainable decisions. Through process of optional modeling, finding possibility of solving problems by consideration of specificity uniqueness of research area.

In general, concept of area simulation (modeling) is coincided to scientific thinking and regarded as object modeling; imitation is transferred from object to object based on features of processes and events of the field. Models launch according to modern scientific knowledge of the field - shape, size, time factors and implementation methods.

One of the frequently implemented methods - physical method, when/where real object is replaced by its enlarged or reduced interpretation based on field research, thus characteristics of processes transferred from model to object due to their similarity. In many cases approach of this model based on study of social and economic development. To some extent can be represented as multiple system of separate models. Systematic approach gives potential for adoption along with model approach of inquiry of social and economic development at the research area. Thereby social and economic development of analysis area is need for groundwork in context of scrutiny of natural phenomena and environmental contemplation. Complexity of social and economic processes/events, influence of objective and subjective factors on development studies can be chosen as a methodology for modeling of entanglement for observations and measurements of general features beyond measuring of numerous events.

Potential of the territorial development in Absheron peninsula identification of key indicators for assessment of dynamic development at the field and analyze economic conditions. Inquiry of factors of development of the Absheron peninsula at the field of economic and social aspects also examine complexes of environmental protection as stated by scientific methodologies.

Absheron peninsula most developed region of Republic of Azerbaijan for cross-functional industries (petrochemical, gas, electrotechnical construction materials), cultivated agriculture continuously expanded at the economic region. Considering on Absheron peninsula's rich hydrocarbon reserves and since centuries existing fossil fuel/chemical industries with potential of creation of new modern petrochemical complexes, additional progress on dynamic and rapid development based on waste oil and industrial waste.

Assessment of damages to soils of Absheron peninsula originating at atmospheric air and water sources as an outcomes of activities of petrochemical enterprises are necessary. Development of oil industry of Absheron peninsula acting important part in Country's budget as one of oldest oil-drilling areas. Peninsula set-

ties exceptional position in manufacturing of high quality raw oil reserves of entire world's oil industry. Investigations present facts regarding on surrounding areas exposed to contamination, according to efficient development of petrochemical industry [5, 6]. Soils under oil and chemical industrial enterprises are evaluated in comparative conditions, depending on quantity of exceedingly harmful chemical substances/properties at ground layers. Fertility of soils vary with number of natural and anthropogenic factors and entertains crucial position in estimation of oil-polluted contamination by petroleum industry; under these circumstances taints of land covers effected by chemical substances, re-cultivation process is required. Scientific territorial studies of Absheron peninsula continue with development of assessments and academic work on contaminated soils [11].

Comprehensive approach to analyzes of environmental disturbance segregates soil studies of Absheron peninsula by the same-type lithological structures and pollution levels. Ecological valuation of contaminated soils of Absheron peninsula's advanced petrochemical industry cover elementary, most generalized and integrated features of pollution. The technological range of pollution has been identified and explained related on environmentally-safe opinion of natural parameters of contamination [2].

Assessment of natural heritage implies many areas of natural values: geographical, ecological, biological, cultural etc. Essential elements cover distinctive landscapes, sole geological creations, unique biological species, civilized consequences to aboriginal population groups. Estimation approaches activate data of field expeditions, preparation of maps, analysis of social and cultural inspections of research regions.

Conclusion

Being in charge with number/s of preservation of natural monuments overcome to protection and conservation of natural resources and landscape units.

Major purpose highlighted on:

- conservation of planning aspects in Absheron peninsula - design of evaluation programmes applying on scientific data with core sides on habitat protection and landscapes' sustainability;
- juridical and political points - implementing legal questions and acts for prevention of natural ecosystems and components in study region, as well as traditional customs;
- civic participation cases in Peninsula Absheron - collaboration with residents and shareholders during decision-making activities to secure reflection and encouragement of administration of natural components;
- observations and investigations of statuses of units of natural heritage in research area - sustainable monitoring via based upon study and inquiry of dynamics of changes;
- development and recognition of significance of natural heritage over expansion of awareness of local

communities of Absheron through educational projects, instruction of markers, extension of entertainments, contribution of preservation endeavors;

- balanced implementation of actions aimed on land planning, rural development, soil management, tourism activities for decreasing of negative influence on natural landscapes and natural monuments in consideration district;
- global collaboration directed on international conservation aspects, knowledgeable maintenances, partnership attempts for interests of society and nature in respect of unique importance of Absheron;
- productive governance of balanced progress on natural heritage of Absheron with estimation of core points of sustainability, pointing up in context of worldwide integration.

References

1. Bayramova L. Ecological aspects of protection of groundwater resources of Nakhichevan (in Russian) [Байрамова Л.А. Экологические аспекты охраны ресурсов подземных вод в Нахичеванской АР]. Symbol of Science / Omega Science - International Center for Innovative Researches N5/2016 Volume 3. Ufa, Bashkortostan. pp. 262 - 264 (co-author Seyidov İ.)
2. Bayramova L. To the question of protection of natural and cultural heritage in Azerbaijan (in Russian) [Байрамова Л.А. К вопросу об охране природного и культурного наследия в Азербайджане] International Scientific Journal N4/2016 Kiev/Ukraine 2016 (co-author İsmayilova Kh.)
3. İmanov F. Alakbarov A. Modern changes and integrated management of water resources of Azerbaijan (In Azerbaijani). AzerSu OSJC and BSU. Baku, 2017
4. Kahriz rehabilitation Project. IOM Azerbaijan/UN. Baku, 2024
5. Mammadov G., et al. 2018. Guidelines for mapping interactive electronic soils and ecological assessment of soils based on CiS technologies. Science publishing house, Baku, 2019. 80 pages
6. Mammadov G., Ahadov D., Mammadov Z. Preparation of soil maps and ecological assessment maps of soils of the territories of Azerbaijan liberated from occupation. Baku, 2022
7. Madatzade A., Shykhliniy E. Climate of Azerbaijan [Климат Азербайджана - под ред. А.А. Мадатзаде и Э.М. Шыхлинского]. Baku, 1968.
8. Mammadov R. Hasanov M. Climate of Azerbaijan as a natural treasure. <https://irs-az.com> 4(19), 2014, pp. 23 - 29
9. Museyibov M. Landscapes of Republic of Azerbaijan [Azərbaycanın landsaftları (2014) in Azerbaijani, Ландшафты Азербайджана (2014) in Russian]. Baku, Publishing House ELM. Baku, 2014
10. Ragimov Kh., Hasanov M. Assessment of impact of expected climate changes on environment and population of Azerbaijan (in Russian). Proceedings of the Geographic Society of Azerbaijan. [Рагимов Х.Ш., Гасанов М.С. Оценка воздействия ожидаемых изменений климата на окружающую среду и

население Азербайджана. Труды Географического Общества Азербайджана. Том XVIII]. Baku, 2013

11. Agro-climatic atlas of Azerbaijan [Агроклиматический атлас Азербайджанской Республики]. Baku, 1993

12. Eyubov A. Hadjiyev G. Climatic resources of Azerbaijan [Эйюбов А.Д., Гаджиев Г.А. Климатические ресурсы Азербайджанской ССР] Baku, 1984

123. First National Data of Republic of Azerbaijan on UN Frame Convention on Climate Changes

[Первое Национальное Сообщение Азербайджанской Республики по Рамочной Конвенции ООН об Изменениях Климата]. Baku, 2000

14. Second National Data of Republic of Azerbaijan on UN Frame Convention on Climate Changes. [Второе Национальное Сообщение Азербайджанской Республики по Рамочной Конвенции ООН об изменениях климата]. Baku, 2010.